

SOCIAL SCIENCES

NICHE TOURISM, BULGARIA AND NATURE HERITAGE

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Abstract

Introduction: Bulgaria is among the world's richest countries in thermal, herbal, and Thalasso resources. This wealth is attributed to various natural factors, including the Balkans' geothermal axis, which makes the country home to some of the world's most significant hot springs. The development of thermal tourism in Bulgaria dates back to the opening of the first mineral bath in Bankia in 1905. Today, more than 8,000 students are enrolled in tourism and tourism-related programs in Bulgaria. However, there is a significant shortage of specialized professionals in niche tourism—not only in Bulgaria and the Balkans but globally. **Methods:** The research was conducted in 2022 among 121 individuals, with 102 providing complete responses. The experts' opinions were assessed using an adapted version of the Survey Questionnaire, designed for online use with Google Drive tools. **Results:** Our research highlights an urgent need for specialised training programs to address the skill gaps in the wellness industry. Future professionals must acquire a comprehensive foundation of theoretical knowledge and practical competencies to effectively manage, organize, and implement various wellness procedures, therapies, and programs based on natural resources. To ensure high-quality service, wellness professionals must demonstrate exceptional expertise in delivering customized wellness solutions that align with consumer needs and preferences. **Discussion:** Today there is a growing shift towards more meaningful and health-conscious travel experiences. This opens up opportunities for innovative and specialized tourism products, such as medical wellness & SPA, or climate therapy tourism, which offer not only relaxation but also real benefits for physical and mental health. **Conclusion:** The results analysis we conclude give evidences about the Positive Effects of the Nature heritage on SPA & Thalasso Tourism. In same time, improve the crucial need of specialised staff for the field.

Keywords: Niche services, natural resources, educational programs, Spa practices, Aromatherapy, health promotion, Wellness for All.

INTRODUCTION

Throughout human history, the pursuit of health restoration has been a key motivator for individuals to travel long distances in search of treatments and cures (2, 8, 9). Global supply and demand trends also influence spa and health tourism, with the industry's development largely shaped by the availability and quality of natural resources, as well as socio-cultural and economic factors (5, 12, 14, 15). Bulgaria is among the world's richest countries in thermal, herbal, and Thalasso resources (1, 6, 10, 16). This wealth is attributed to various natural factors, including the Balkans' geothermal axis, which makes the country home to some of the world's most significant hot springs—such as Hisar, Sapareva Banya, Velingrad, and mineral springs in Haskovo, Burgas, Ognianovo, Varna, Varshets, and Sandanski. These thermal resources make Bulgaria an ideal destination for SPA and Thalasso (Black Sea lye) tourism (3, 13, 7, 19).

The development of thermal tourism in Bulgaria dates back to the opening of the first mineral bath in Bankia in 1905. Various tourism educational institutions have been operating at different levels, with higher tourism programs emerging in the 1960s and expanding further in the mid-1990s (4, 11, 17, 22). Today, more than 8,000 students are enrolled in tourism and tourism-related programs in Bulgaria (18, 20, 21). However, there is a significant shortage of specialized professionals in niche tourism—not only in Bulgaria and the Balkans but globally (21, 23).

METHODS

The research was conducted in 2022 among 121 individuals, with 102 providing complete responses. All participants were Bulgarian, aged between 21 and 53 years, including 52 men and 50 women. The average age of the respondents was 33.5 years. For the study, the target group was categorized based on age (21–31 years, 32–41 years, 42–53 years), gender, work experience (less than 7 years, 8–15 years, and over 16 years), and professional rank (executives, managers, and students in the field of niche tourism). The experts' opinions were assessed using an adapted version of the Survey Questionnaire, designed for online use with Google Drive tools. To achieve the research objectives, a psychometric assessment test was employed. The psychometric evaluation of experts' opinions was based on numerical values assigned to each question, reflecting the quantity of relevant attributes. The questions were sorted according to the number of properties they represented, resulting in a ranking scale that determined the relative significance of the studied factors for the quality of services and centers within Bulgarian niche tourism.

RESULTS

Niche tourism demands a high level of professional competence, requiring specialised knowledge and skills that align with the evolving demands of the job market (23). Following multiple reforms in the Bulgarian education system, a List of Professional Fields was introduced in 2002, categorising Niche Tourism (based on natural heritage) under the professional field

of Healthcare and Sports with designation 7. Our research highlights an urgent need for specialised training programs to address the skill gaps in the wellness industry. Future professionals must acquire a comprehensive foundation of theoretical knowledge and practical competencies to effectively manage, organize, and implement various wellness procedures, therapies, and programs based on natural resources. To ensure high-quality service, wellness professionals must demonstrate exceptional expertise in delivering customized wellness solutions that align with consumer needs and preferences. A key finding of our study emphasizes the necessity of strengthening professional collaborations between academic institutions, vocational education and training (VET) providers, secondary schools, and professional training bodies. Establishing a bridge between theory, wellness business, and industry sectors is crucial for integrating real-world experience into educational curricula, ensuring that future professionals gain hands-on practice in authentic professional environments tailored to various natural resources. Furthermore, our study identifies wellness facility indicators

that determine high-quality services and consumer preferences. These indicators are ranked based on significance according to customer perceptions and expert evaluations as follows: 1. The more important on first place is "The highly qualified and trained personnel". The selective efficiency must be according to specific criteria like a level of education or certification, the specialised skills and the practical experience. This indicator is with high significance (raking one, with 86% of expert's regard with a personal point of view and 553 units). 2. The next indicator is the "Standardisation of the quality services" according the EU standards about wellness & spa locations/destinations" (Ranks two, with 65, 5% of expert's regard with a personal point of view and 473 units). We presenting the significance based on the scale of studied indicators during the quality assessment with customers and experts point of view. For the first time, the Bulgarian educational and scientific accomplishments in the sector of wellness and spa are showcased (see Fig.1).

Figure 1: Importance range scale based on customers and experts point of view

In the Centre for Excellence in Creative and Recreation industry ("Heritage BG"), the 40-second laboratory is modelled according to the global science studies based on water healthy influence and accredited

Bulgarian educational model for training of specialised staff for wellness and Niche tourism (see Fig.2).

Figure 2. Architectonics of the Bulgarian education & science model for the Wellness & Spa & Thalasso culture.

This initiative aims to attract young people in Bulgaria by offering opportunities for European and multinational professional realization through specialized bachelor's, master's, and doctoral programs. These programs align with newly incorporated job positions in the National Classification of Professions and Job Positions (NCPP, 2014), including:

- ✓ Spa Center Manager/Advisor (ID: 1431-6022)
- ✓ Wellness Center Manager/Advisor (ID: 1431-6023)
- ✓ Thalasso Center Manager/Advisor (ID: 1431-6024)

For the first time in Europe, doctoral programs in Wellness and Health Promotion, as well as a bachelor's program in Wellness consultant (launched in July 2019), have been introduced. Additionally, specialized education in Technology and Entrepreneurship in Wellness and Niche Tourism (from 8th to 12th grade) was established in December 2018.

Furthermore, this initiative introduces two structured educational verticals for specialized personnel in Bulgarian niche tourism, classified under:

- ✓ 7.6. Sport
- ✓ 7.5. Health Care

A key social mission of the new students is to promote a daily healthy lifestyle through volunteer activities in the Wellness, Spa, and Thalasso Culture programs at NSA "V. Levski". They also collaborate within the Blue Cluster and Cluster Bridge networks, led by young wellness and spa specialists and doctoral students in Bulgaria.

Here we analyse the Benefits of Thermal Resources in Bulgaria as a Destination for SPA and Thalasso Tourism. Bulgaria is among the world's richest countries in thermal, herbal, and Thalasso (Black Sea

lye) resources, making it a premier spa and wellness tourism destination.

1. *The country's* abundant natural wealth, combined with a long-standing tradition in thermal practices, provides a solid foundation for the development of high-quality wellness and medical tourism services.

2. *Unique Thermal and Thalasso Resources in Bulgaria*

Bulgaria's geothermal axis supplies over 600 mineral springs, varying in composition and temperature (from 20°C to over 100°C). Key thermal destinations include:

- ✓ Hisarya (52°C)
- ✓ Sapareva Banya (103°C) – the hottest geyser in the Balkans
- ✓ Velingrad (97°C) – "The Spa Capital of the Balkans"
- ✓ Sandanski (temperate mineral waters, ideal for respiratory therapy)
- ✓ Varna & Burgas – combining mineral springs with Thalasso therapy from Black Sea salt and lye
- ✓ Additionally, Black Sea lye, a unique marine product with high concentrations of magnesium, calcium, and sodium, is widely used in detox, anti-inflammatory, and pain relief treatments.

3. *Benefits of Thermal and Thalasso Tourism in Bulgaria*

3.1. *Health Benefits*

Musculoskeletal & Joint Therapy – Thermal mineral waters help in treating arthritis, rheumatism, and sports injuries.

Respiratory & Skin Treatments – Inhalation therapies with mineral-rich steam improve conditions such as asthma and bronchitis, while Black Sea lye supports skin rejuvenation.

Cardiovascular & Nervous System Support – The therapeutic properties of thermal waters regulate blood circulation and relieve stress.

Detoxification & Anti-aging – The minerals found in thermal springs and Black Sea mud stimulate cellular regeneration and remove toxins.

3.2. Economic & Tourism Benefits

Year-Round Tourism – Unlike seasonal tourism, spa and wellness tourism operates 365 days a year, ensuring economic sustainability.

Competitive Advantage in the European Market – Bulgaria offers affordable, high-quality wellness services compared to Western European spa destinations.

Job Creation & Local Business Growth – The wellness industry boosts employment in hospitality, healthcare, and wellness services.

3.3. Cultural & Sustainability Benefits

Preservation of Traditional Healing Practices – Many wellness centers incorporate Bulgarian balneology traditions, herbal medicine, and essential oils from lavender, rose, and mountain herbs.

Sustainable & Eco-Tourism Development – Thermal tourism relies on natural, renewable resources with minimal environmental impact.

4. Challenges & Opportunities

Challenges:

- ✓ Lack of specialized personnel in niche wellness tourism
- ✓ Need for improved infrastructure and marketing strategies
- ✓ Competition from well-established European spa destinations

Opportunities:

- ✓ Developing integrated wellness resorts combining balneotherapy, Thalasso treatments, and medical spa programs
- ✓ Promoting Bulgaria as a premium wellness retreat for European and Middle Eastern tourists
- ✓ Enhancing international partnerships and investments in the wellness industry

DISCUSSION

After the COVID-19 pandemic, tourism trends changed significantly, with the wellness and SPA industries emerging as some of the few sectors that recorded an 18% growth, even in times of financial instability. Although digitalization has standardized tourist behavior, making mass tourism more predictable and market-driven, the new wave of travelers is increasingly seeking personalized services focused on health and well-being. Before the pandemic, tourists were often passive spectators, guided by mass consumer preferences, with little interest in the history or value of the destinations they visited. However, today there is a growing shift towards more meaningful and health-conscious travel experiences. This opens up opportunities for innovative and specialized tourism products, such as medical wellness & SPA, or climate therapy tourism, which offer not only relaxation but also real benefits for physical and mental health.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results analysis we conclude the Positive Effects of the Nature heritage on SPA & Thalasso Tourism, as following:

➤ Bulgaria's abundant thermal and Thalasso resources position it as a leading destination for spa, wellness, and medical tourism.

➤ The country has the potential to expand its global market share by improving infrastructure and sustainable development practices.

➤ Bulgaria become an educational leader for specialised staff with accredited training and higher education programs (5 in the last 7 years: “Bachelor”, “Master” & “Doctoral” degree programs).

➤ With increasing demand for natural health solutions, Bulgaria can strengthen its reputation as a top wellness hub in Europe.

Note:

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